

GOALS AND TASKS OF TEACHING MUSIC TO PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS AT SCHOOL

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Annotation: This article describes in detail the role of music education in the formation of children as mature individuals, the effective organization of music culture lessons by music teachers, the methods of effective organization of students in lessons, the methods and structure of the formation of music culture in the minds of students in music lessons.

Keywords: interest, mission, work, spirituality, psyche, voice, student, analysis, methodology, tradition, music lesson, education.

The attention paid at the state level to the development of national culture in the construction of a new Uzbekistan is of great importance. In this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan According to Sh. Mirziyoev, “The level of development of our people is assessed primarily by our national culture. In this sense, culture is the image of our people, our society. As we begin to create a new image of Uzbekistan, we must begin with the development of our national culture.”[1].

The Uzbek Center for the Study of Cultural Heritage Abroad and the Center for New History of Uzbekistan are being set up. Great attention is paid to the development of reading culture, culture and art, and creative schools and centers named after our great artists are being established in the regions. Systematic measures are being taken to further popularize folklore and amateur arts, and to develop innovative areas of culture and the arts. In this regard, President Shavkat Mirziyoev said, “If culture and art do not develop in the country, society will not develop. It is important to develop the field of culture and arts, to increase the prestige of the Uzbek national culture and art in the world, to realize the potential of young talents. Indeed, when art and culture live, the nation and the people, the whole of humanity, live in peace”.[2]

Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts. In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PD - 3391 of November 17, 2017 “ On measures to further develop the art of the Uzbek national makom”, August 26, 2018 Resolution No. PD - 3920 “ On measures for innovative development of the arts ”, Resolution No. PD-4038 of November 28, 2018 “ On approval of the Concept of further development of national culture in

the Republic of Uzbekistan”, 2019 Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1019 of December 19, 2019 “ On approval of the Program for improving the activities of museums in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2020-2021”, November 23, 2019 Resolution of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 26, 2019 “ On approval of the activities of the Erkin Vakhidov Memorial Museum and the Treasury House-Museum” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 630 [3] of May 30, 2019 “ On the organization of the activities of the state museum-reserves Sarmishsay ”, “Shakhrisabz”, “Termez” and “ Kokand ” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 443 of April 21 [4] , 2020 “On measures to further increase the efficiency of the fine and applied arts” Resolution No. PD - 4688 of May 26, 2020 “Culture Decree No. PD-6000 of May 23 [5], 2020 “On measures to further enhance the role and influence of the arts in society” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 325 of June 9, 2021 and “Martyrs’ Memory” Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 357 of February 2, 2022 “On support of the Moat Fund” The normative legal acts adopted, such as Resolution No. PD – 1 2 of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan [6] are becoming increasingly important.

Along with all the subjects taught at school, music culture lessons, which are a component of sophistication education, are of great importance in raising the young generation to be mature in all aspects. Music expresses human feelings and desires in its own artistic language and actively influences the child's emotions. Music has a direct impact on mastering other subjects at school. Music, as a living art form, reflects the times, life, nature and human feelings and desires. It makes him happy, makes him think and helps him to get food from life. As Abu Nasr Farabi, the grandfather of our national culture, said, "This science is useful for the health of the body." Our grandfather, Sheikh Saadi, said, "Music is the companion of the human soul." Therefore, we should start teaching music from elementary school students. Because the foundation of music education is laid in primary school. The main goal of teaching music in primary school is to teach primary school students the ability to study music based on the laws of beauty and to inculcate musical culture in them. Music culture lessons in primary grades are an integral part of the moral-aesthetic education system of general education. Music education in primary grades aims to implement the following tasks:

1. Instilling a passion for music in students and developing their musical abilities, a sense of rhythm, forming musical learning, memory, attention and artistic taste.

2. Cultivating students' love for our national musical heritage and, through it, for the Motherland.

3. Cultivating students' artistic creativity. To develop students' ability to see beauty and bring beauty to life. Listening to music is of great importance in enriching students' musical creativity, impressions, and expanding their imaginations. Music listening takes place from the beginning to the end of the lesson, because all types of activities of music culture lessons (singing, performing musical rhythmic movements, listening to music) are expressed by means of the melody created in musical sounds. Music culture lessons help elementary school students to perceive the beautiful things around them and to form their spiritual worldview. Based on the "State Educational Standards for Primary Education", a program was developed for music along with all other subjects. The content of the new program reflects the full use of the heritage of our national music, popular folk tunes and songs, lapar, epics and today's modern music. The main theme of the program is "Music and Life". The themes of the year, quarter and lesson are subordinated to the theme of the year and form a whole in terms of content. This requires the elementary music teacher to update the content of the work. In order to conduct lessons in the content of the new program, the music teacher must improve his musical theoretical knowledge, because it is necessary to increase students' interest in music lessons, to educate the young generation in the spirit of love for the Motherland, and to make them spiritual and enlightened.

The teacher is considered to be the leader in bringing him to adulthood. Everyone knows that not every artist can teach music at school. In order to become a primary school music teacher, one must be a person who loves his profession and children, has a high culture, and a broad outlook. He should have deep knowledge in the practical fields of pedagogy, psychology, and children's physiology. The range of activity of a music teacher in primary grades is wide. Along with music culture lessons, he should also organize and manage types of music education outside the classroom.

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